

經濟部水利署水利規劃試驗所

下一代淹水潛勢圖產製及模型建置教育訓練

使用 DelftFM 進行最小模型建置介紹

主講人 徐志宏 博士

2023/04/28

最小模式 建置

二維模式

二維模式 + 一維河道 + 一維下水道

二維模式

建模步驟：

1. 定義模擬區域
2. 載入地形資料
3. 產生計算網格並內插地形高程
4. 定義邊界條件
5. 執行模擬
6. 檢核模擬成果

模擬區域與資料

Amsterdam →

0 5 10 km

Elevation (m)

Vinkeveense
Plassen

啟動D-Flow並建立FM Model

Open

Browse

Recent Projects

2DF_CL1.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\SOBEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-03 04:49:20.065
2DF.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\SOBEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-03 04:44:28.317
Project1.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\SOBEK_DATA\SBK_SEWER	2023-04-03 00:40:23.339
Rural1D2D.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\Rural_workflows	2023-04-03 00:39:22.449
Rural1D2D_2.dsproj	C:\Users\aaaronch\Desktop	2023-04-02 05:03:03.419
2D_rural_dike_overtopping.dsproj	E:\F_MODEL_PG\03D\2023\tutorial and Test Data\1D2D\Workflow - Rural material\Rural\Projects	2023-04-02 03:49:14.767
1D2D_rural_with_output.dsproj	E:\F_MODEL_PG\03D\2023\tutorial and Test Data\1D2D\Workflow - Rural material\Rural\Projects	2023-04-02 03:49:14.183
Rural1D2D_2.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\Rural_workflows	2023-04-02 03:42:28.145
Rural1.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\Rural_workflows	2023-04-02 02:07:15.170
tmp1.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\SOBEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-01 17:27:37.511
2DF_1D_Flood4.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\SOBEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-01 22:04:55.739
2DF_1D_Flood3.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\SOBEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-03 00:28:18.814
2DF_1D_Flood5.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\SOBEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-01 17:16:49.128
2DF_1D_Flood2.dsproj	D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\SOBEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-02 04:25:16.899
2DF_1D_Flood.dsproj		

Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D 2022.04

General

Empty project Unstructured grid Map (World)

New model

Integrated model **FM model**

New model from import

Dimr import GWSW import Sobek 2 import

命名並建立專案

Open

Browse

Recent Projects

2DF_CL1.dsjproj D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\S0BEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-03 04:49:20.065
2DF.dsjproj D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\S0BEK_DATA\tutorial2Dflooding	2023-04-03 04:44:28.317
Project1.dsjproj D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\S0BEK_DATA\SBK_SEWER	2023-04-03 00:40:23.339
Rural1D2D.dsjproj D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\Rural_workflows	2023-04-03 00:39:22.449
Rural1D2D_2.dsjproj C:\Users\aaronc\H\Desktop	2023-04-02 05:03:03.419
2D_rural_dike_overshooting.dsjproj E:\F_MODEL_PG\D3D\2023\tutorial and Test Data\1D2D\Workflow - Rural material\Rural\Projects	2023-04-02 03:45
1D2D_rural_with_output.dsjproj E:\F_MODEL_PG\D3D\2023\tutorial and Test Data\1D2D\Workflow - Rural material\Rural\Projects	2023-04-02 03:45
Rural1D2D_2.dsjproj D:\OneDrive\MD_D3D\Rural_workflows	2023-04-02 03:42:28.145
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2DF_1D_Flood.dsjproj	2023-04-02 04:25:16.899

Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D 2022.04

General

Empty project Unstructured grid Map (World)

New model

Dimr import GWSW import Sobek 2 import

 FM model X

Creates a new standalone flexible mesh model

Model name

Coordinate system Amersfoort / RD New ...

 Create

儲存專案於指定資料夾

Project1* - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Info

Product name: Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D
Version: 2022.04
Copyright: © Deltares 2022
Email: software.support@deltares.nl
Telephone: +31 (0)88 335 8100

User name: aaronchh
Machine name:
Operating system:
Processor count:
Process type:

Save As 儲存專案檔

Application plugins

- Delta Shell Common Tools Plugin: Plugin for common views and data.
- Delta Shell Project File Plugin: Provides implementation of the data access to the Delta Shell project files using NHibernate library.
- Hydro Model Plugin: Provides functionality to create and run integrated models.
- D-Rainfall Runoff Plugin: Allows to simulate lumped rainfall runoff models, such as Sacramento and HBV.
- D-Real Time Control Plugin: Allows to simulate Real-Time Control for models, such as D-Flow 1D.
- D-Flow Flexible Mesh Plugin: Allows to simulate 2D/3D flow of water in rivers, channels, lakes, estuarine & coastal areas and sea.
- Grid Editor Plugin: Editor for creating and changing unstructured grids.
- GWSW Importer Application Plugin
- SOBEK Network Import Plugin: Plugin that provides functionality to import from the SOBEK2 Network format.
- NetCDF Plugin: NetCDF storage for multidimensional data.
- Hydro Region Plugin: Provides editing functionality for geometrical information in the hydro region.
- Delta Shell Scripting Plugin: Provides scripting functionality.
- SharpMap GIS Plugin: Provides common GIS functionality.

選擇專案儲存路徑

File name: Project1.dsproj
Save as type: Delta Shell Project File (*.dsproj)

設定專案名稱

Save Cancel

Version: 4.9.0.2873.3e1746f
File version: :1.1.0.0

Version: 2.0.0.1485.8037937
File version: :1.1.0.0

Version: 4.9.0.2873
File version: :1.1.0.0

Version: 4.9.0.2873
File version: :3.5.0.0

Version: 4.9.0.2873.3e1746f
File version: :3.5.0.0

Version: 4.9.0.2873
File version: :1.0.0.0

Version: 4.9.0.2873
File version: :1.1.0.0

Version: 1.1.0.1
File version: :1.1.0.1

Version: 4.9.0.2873
File version: :4.5.0.0

Version: 4.9.0.2873
File version: :3.5.0.0

Version: 4.9.0.2873
File version: :3.5.0.0

Version: 2.0.0.1485.8037937
File version: :1.1.0.0

Version: 2.0.0.1485.8037937
File version: :1.2.1.0

Delta Shell Project Explorer (UI)
TreeView representation of a project

Delta Shell Scripting Plugin (UI)
Provides scripting functionality.

展開常用工具列

展開常用工具列

指定專案投影座標系統

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The 'Map' menu is highlighted with a red circle (1). The 'Map Coordinate System' option is selected in the 'Spatial Operations' toolbar, also highlighted with a red circle (2). The 'Choose coordinate system' dialog box is open, showing a list of coordinate systems. 'Amersfoort / RD New [EPSG:28992]' is selected, highlighted with a red circle (3) and a red box (4). The 'OK' button is highlighted with a red circle (5). The dialog box contains the following text:

```
PROJ4 +proj=sterea +lat_0=52.15616055555555 +lon_0=-5.387638888888889  
+k=0.9999079 +x_0=155000 +y_0=463000 +llps=bessel  
+towgs84=565.2369,50.0087,465.658,-0.406857,0.350733,-1.87035,4.0812  
+units=m +no_defs
```

WKT:
PROJCS["Amersfoort / RD New",
GEOCS["Amersfoort",
DATUM["Amersfoort",
SPHEROID["Bessel 1841",6377397.155,299.1528128,
AUTHORITY["EPSG","7004"]],
TOWGS84[565.2369,50.0087,465.658,-0.406857,0.350733,-
1.87035,4.0812],
AUTHORITY["EPSG","6289"]],
PRIMEM["Greenwich",0],
AUTHORITY["EPSG","8901"]],
UNIT["degree",0.0174532925199433,
AUTHORITY["EPSG","3122"]],
AUTHORITY["EPSG","4289"]],
PROJECTION["Oblique_Stereographic"],
PARAMETER["latitude_of_origin",52.15616055555555],
PARAMETER["central_meridian",-5.387638888888889],
PARAMETER["scale_factor",0.9999079],
PARAMETER["false_easting",155000],
PARAMETER["false_northing",463000],
UNIT["metre",1],
AUTHORITY["EPSG","9001"]],
AXIS["X",EAST],
AXIS["Y",NORTH],
AUTHORITY["EPSG","28992"]]

載入模擬範圍shapefile

The screenshot illustrates the steps to load a shapefile into the Delft3D FM Suite software. The interface is divided into several panels:

- Ribbon:** The 'Grid' tab (1) is active, showing various grid-related tools. The 'Polygons' button (4) is highlighted in the ribbon.
- File Explorer:** An 'Open' dialog box (5) is open, showing the file '2D_OF_msk.shp' selected in the 'D:\FLOW > DEMO > SHP' directory. The 'Open' button (6) is highlighted.
- Map View:** The 'Map' panel on the right shows the 'Grid editor' and 'Polygons' layers checked, indicating the shapefile is being processed.

Numbered callouts (1-6) highlight the following steps:

1. Select the 'Grid' tab in the ribbon.
2. Click the 'Edit' button in the ribbon.
3. Click the 'Import Grid' button in the ribbon.
4. Click the 'Polygons' button in the ribbon.
5. Select the file '2D_OF_msk.shp' in the file explorer.
6. Click the 'Open' button in the file explorer.

載入basemap

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The 'Map' tab is selected in the top menu bar, indicated by a red circle with the number '1'. The 'Add dutch layers' menu is open, with 'Aerial photo' highlighted, also indicated by a red circle with the number '2'. The main map area shows a blue polygon representing a flow domain. The interface includes a Project tree on the left, a Properties panel, and a Messages window at the bottom.

Project Tree:

- Project1
 - FlowFM
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

Properties Panel (Area):

- General
 - Name: Area
- Misc
 - Coordinate System: <empty>

Messages Window:

Message	Time
Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:28:42.743
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:28:42.535
Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:28:38.637
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:20:06.815
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:19:55.714
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:19:55.148

產生Mesh

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The 'GIS' tab is active, and the 'Generate' menu is open, showing various grid generation options. The 'Rectangular grid within polygon' option is highlighted. The map shows a complex polygonal area with a grid overlay. The 'Map' panel on the right shows the 'Grid editor' and 'Mesh' options checked. The 'Messages' panel at the bottom shows several status messages.

Generate Menu Options:

- Curvilinear grid (orthogonal)
- Curvilinear grid (orthogonal)
- Curvilinear grid (transfinite)
- Rectangular grid
- Triangular grid within polygon
- Rectangular grid within polygon**
- Grid from samples
- Grid refinement based on samples
- Curvilinear grid from polygon
- Curvilinear grid from triangle

Map Panel:

- Grid editor
- Mesh
- Polygons
- Splines
- Land boundaries
- Samples
- FlowFM
- 1D
- 2D
- BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS
 - standaard
 - grijs
 - pastel
 - water

Messages:

Message	Time
Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:28:42.743
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:28:42.535
Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:28:38.637
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:20:06.815
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:19:55.714
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:19:55.148

產生Mesh (輸入grid size)

The screenshot displays the 'Rectangular grid within polygon' dialog box in the Delft3D FM Suite software. The dialog box contains the following fields and values:

- Grid angle: 0
- Angular deg.: 0
- x Grid block size: 150 m
- y Grid block size: 150 m

A red box highlights the 'x Grid block size' and 'y Grid block size' fields, with a circled '1' next to it. Another red box highlights the 'Generate' button, with a circled '2' next to it. The background shows a map of a coastal area with a grid overlay.

刪除模擬區外之Mesh

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 interface. The 'Delete mesh' dropdown menu is open, showing the following options:

- Delete faces outside selected polygon
- All faces whose circumcenter are inside the polygon
- Delete vertices inside the polygon
- All faces whose circumcenter are inside the polygon
- All faces completely inside the polygon

Annotations on the right side of the image:

- ① 勾選 (Checkmark) - points to the first option: Delete faces outside selected polygon
- ② 點選 (Click) - points to the second option: All faces whose circumcenter are inside the polygon

The interface also shows a project tree on the left, a map view with a grid overlay, and a messages panel at the bottom.

刪除模擬區外之Mesh

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The main window shows a map with a grid overlay. A red box highlights the 'Delete mesh' icon in the 'Grid' toolbar. A tooltip for this icon reads: 'Delete mesh' and 'Deletes all vertices inside the (selected) polygons'. A red circle with the number '1' is placed next to the tooltip. A text box with the Chinese characters '點擊刪除Mesh' (Click to delete Mesh) is also present. The interface includes a 'Project' tree on the left, a 'Properties' panel for the selected 'Area', a 'Messages' panel at the bottom, and a 'Map' panel on the right with various layer settings.

GIS Config
DIMR

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid Edit

Boundary grid Merge Subtract Clip Generate Insert Delete Vertices Move Delete Delete mesh Delete samples in polygons Orthogonalization Refine Merge overlapping grid Flip edges Show Orthogonalization Show Smoothness Import Polygons Export Grid Advanced options

Start/... Geometry Tools

Project Project1 FlowFM General 1D 2D Area Grid Bed Level Initial Conditions Boundary Conditions Physical Parameters Sources and Sinks 1D2D Links Output

Properties Area General Name Area Misc Coordinate System <empty>

Messages Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj 2023-04-04 00:28:38.637 Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output 2023-04-04 00:20:06.815 Project Project1 saved 2023-04-04 00:19:55.714 2023-04-04 00:19:55.714 Project Project1 saved

Name Name of Area.

Map Use focused layer Map Grid editor Mesh Polygons Splines Land boundaries Samples FlowFM 1D 2D BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS standaard grijs pastel water

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

完成編輯Mesh

GIS Config DIMR

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid

Boundary grid Merge Subtract Clip Generate Insert Delete Vertices Move Delete Edges Delete mesh Delete samples in polygons Orthogonalization Refine grid Merge overlapping vertices Flip edges Show Orthogonalization Show Smoothness Import Polygons Export Grid Advanced options Advanced

Start... Edit Polygons Splines Land boundaries Refine polygon Geometry Tools

Project 點擊結束編輯

FlowFM X

Project1

- FlowFM
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

Properties

Area

General

Name Area

Misc

Coordinate System <empty>

Save changes

Do you want to save the changes that were made to the grid

確認 Yes No

Messages

- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj 2023-04-04 00:28:38.637
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output 2023-04-04 00:20:06.815
- Project Project1 saved 2023-04-04 00:19:55.714
- 2023-04-04 00:19:55.714 Project Project1 saved

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

載入地形資料

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map view with a yellow grid overlay. The GIS toolbar is visible, with the 'Import' button highlighted. A file selection dialog box is open, showing the file 'bath.xyz' selected. The status bar at the bottom displays messages and a time navigator.

Numbered callouts in the image indicate the following steps:

1. Layer: Bed Level
2. GIS: Spatial Operations
3. GIS: Import
4. File selection dialog: bath.xyz

Messages:

- Project Project1 saved
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output
- Project Project1 saved
- Creating database session ...

Time Navigator:

Time
2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

載入地形資料

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a yellow grid overlay. A dialog box titled "Apply coordinate transformation on da..." is open, with the "Import without transformation (s-s)" option selected. The "OK" button is highlighted with a red box. A red arrow points to the "OK" button, and a text box below it contains the Chinese characters "點擊確認載入" (Click to confirm loading).

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid

Layer Bed Level Polygon Line Points Add

Decor... Edit Add

Project FM_model X

Project1

- FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

Properties

Messages

Message	Time
Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

內插地形高程至計算網格(grid)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window is titled "Project1 - Delf3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)". The GIS menu is open, showing the "Interpolate" option selected, with a sub-menu option "Interpolate selected set" highlighted. Three red circles are overlaid on the interface: (1) around the "Spatial Operations" menu, (2) around the "Interpolate" button, and (3) around the "Interpolate selected set" option. The main map area shows a grid of red and green points overlaid on a geographical map of a coastal area with water bodies and land parcels. The "Operations" panel on the right shows the "Import samples" step. The "Messages" panel at the bottom shows a list of system messages.

GIS

Project1 - Delf3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools

Layer Bed Level

Legend

Decor... Edit Add

Project

FM_model X

Project1

- FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

Properties

Messages

Message	Time
Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

內插地形高程至計算網格(grid)

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid

Layer Bed Level Polygon Line Points Add

Decor... Edit Add

Project FM_model X

Project1

- FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

Properties Sample points import properties

General

- Name Import samples 1
- Enabled True
- Input
 - Input file bath.xyz
 - Source coordinate sy Amersfoort / RD New
- Output
 - Target coordinate sy: Amersfoort / RD New

Input file File from which the sample set is read.

Messages

Icon	Message	Time
Info	Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
Info	Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
Info	Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
Info	Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
Info	Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
Info	Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

Operations

- Bed Level
 - set 1
 - Import samples 1

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

Interpolation operation

Please specify the operation parameters

Pointwise operation: Overwrite where mis

Interpolation method: Triangulation

Spatial Projection Type: 2D

OK Cancel

點擊確認

隱藏地形資料 (顯示網格)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D software interface. The main window shows a map with a blue grid overlay representing the terrain data. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar with various GIS operations (Import, Set Value, Interpolate, Copy to samples, Copy to spatial data, Merge spatial data, Merge Operations, Delete, Gradient, Overwrite Value), and a Project panel on the left. The Project panel shows a tree view of the project structure, including FM_model, General, 1D, 2D, Area, Grid, Bed Level, Initial Conditions, Boundary Conditions, Physical Parameters, Sources and Sinks, 1D2D Links, and Output. The Properties panel on the left shows the 'General' properties of the 'Bed Level' layer, including its name and the number of layers (3). The Messages panel at the bottom shows a list of system messages, including project saving and database creation. The right-hand side of the interface features a Map panel with a list of layers and their visibility settings. The 'Bed Level' layer is highlighted in blue, and a red arrow points to the '取消勾选' (Deselect) button next to it. A red circle with the number '1' is placed over the 'Map' button in the bottom right corner of the interface.

地形資料 →

取消勾选 ②

1

放大顯示區域 (設定邊界條件)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a yellow grid overlay. A red rectangular box highlights a specific area on the grid, labeled with a circled '2'. In the top-left corner, the 'Map' tab is active, and the 'Zoom Next' button is highlighted with a red circle and labeled with a circled '1'. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar with various GIS tools, and a project tree on the left. The right side of the interface shows a 'Map' panel with a list of layers and their properties. The bottom of the window features a 'Messages' panel with a log of system events.

① 選取放大鏡工具

② 框選欲放大之區域

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Project1

- FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped Features
 - BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS
 - standaard
 - grijs
 - pastel
 - water

Messages

- Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dproj saved 2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
- Project Project1 saved 2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dproj 2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output 2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
- Project Project1 saved 2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
- Creating database session ... 2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

Coordinate system: "Amersfoort / RD New" (EPSG: 28992) - Current map coordinates: 124391.844371471, 472387.283060921

設定邊界條件

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a yellow grid overlay. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar with various GIS and modeling tools, and several panels:

- Project Panel:** Shows the project structure, including FM_model, General, 1D, 2D, Area, Grid, Bed Level, Initial Conditions, Boundary Conditions, Physical Parameters, Sources and Sinks, 1D/2D Links, and Output.
- Properties Panel:** Currently empty.
- Map Panel:** Shows the map layers and their visibility. The 'BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS' layer is selected, and its properties are shown in the right-hand panel.
- Messages Panel:** Displays a list of messages, including project saving and model execution status.

The right-hand panel shows the following settings for the 'BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS' layer:

- FM_model
- 1D
- 2D
- Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
- Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
- Sources and Sinks
- 1D/2D Links
- Estimated Grid-snapped Features

The bottom right corner of the interface has tabs for Chart, Region, Map, Operations, and Toolbox.

選取邊界
編輯工具

設定邊界條件

單擊開始繪製

雙擊結束繪製

雙擊邊界進入編輯界面

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Project1

- FM_model
- General
- 1D
- 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundary01
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
- 1D2D Links
- Output

Map

- FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped Features
- BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS
 - standaard
 - grijs
 - pastel
 - water

新增邊界條件

Boundary Condition

Flow: Water level

Geometry

新增水位邊界

Water level

Import from files... Export to files... Combined BC view

No boundary condition defined: to create one, click the '+' button.

Messages

Message	Time
Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

新增邊界條件

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Boundary Condition

Flow: Water level

Description: Forcing type: Time Series

Vertical interpolation type:

Reflection parameter:

Thatcher-Harleman time lag: 00:00:00

Factor: 1.00 [-] Offset: 0.00 m

Location

Support point: Boundary01_0001, Boundary01_0002

Geometry

Water level + Generate series... Import from files... Export to files... Combined BC view

No data defined; to create boundary data, activate a support point.

Generate time series...

Generate new (selected)
Modify existing

Time range

Start: 4/ 4/2023 12:00:00 AM

End: 4/ 4/2023 2:30:00 AM

Timestep: 0 days 0 hours 30 min 0 sec

OK Cancel

Messages

- Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved 2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
- Project Project1 saved 2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj 2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output 2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
- Project Project1 saved 2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
- Creating database session ... 2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

① 新增點位1時序列

② 設定起迄、間隔時間

新增邊界條件

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The main window is titled "Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)". The "Boundary Condition" panel is active, showing the following settings:

- Flow: Water level
- Description: Water level
- Forcing type: Time Series
- Vertical interpolation type: (empty)
- Reflection parameter: (empty)
- Thatcher-Harleman time lag: 00:00:00
- Factor: 1.00 [-]
- Offset: 0.00 m

The "Location" panel shows the support points:

- Support point: Boundary01_0001, Boundary01_0002
- Geometry: (empty)

A dialog box titled "Choose support points" is open, with the following options:

- Apply operation to: Selected support point
- Active support points
- Inactive support points
- All support points

The "OK" button is highlighted with a red box, and a red arrow points to it from the text "點擊確認" (Click to confirm) below the dialog box.

The "Messages" panel at the bottom shows the following logs:

Message	Time
Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

新增邊界條件

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window is titled "Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)". The interface is divided into several panels:

- Project Panel:** Shows a tree view of the project structure, including "FM_model", "General", "1D", "2D", "Area", "Grid", "Bed Level", "Initial Conditions", "Boundary Conditions", "Boundary01", "Physical Parameters", "Sources and Sinks", "1D2D Links", and "Output".
- Boundary Condition Panel:** Shows the configuration for "Boundary01 (Boundary conditions)". The "Flow" is set to "Water level". The "Description" is "Water level". The "Forcing type" is "Time Series". The "Vertical interpolation type" is set to "None". The "Reflection parameter" is "None". The "Thatcher-Harleman time lag" is "00:00:00". The "Factor" is "1.00" and the "Offset" is "0.00" m.
- Location Panel:** Shows the "Support point" as "Boundary01_0001" and "Boundary01_0002". The "Geometry" panel shows a line segment on a map.
- Table:** A table showing the time series data for "WaterLevel [m]". The data is constant at 1.5 m for the entire duration from 00:00:00 to 02:30:00.
- Plot:** A line graph showing "WaterLevel [m]" over "Time [-]". The y-axis ranges from 1.5 to 1.5, and the x-axis ranges from 00:00 to 02:30. The plot shows a constant horizontal line at 1.5 m.
- Messages Panel:** Shows a list of messages, including "Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved", "Project Project1 saved", "Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj", "Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output", "Project Project1 saved", and "Creating database session ...".

An arrow points to the first row of the table, with the text "編輯點位1水位時序列" (Edit point 1 water level time series) below it.

Time [-]	WaterLevel [m]
2023/04/04 00:00:00	1.5
2023/04/04 00:30:00	1.5
2023/04/04 01:00:00	1.5
2023/04/04 01:30:00	1.5
2023/04/04 02:00:00	1.5
2023/04/04 02:30:00	1.5

新增邊界條件

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Boundary Condition

Flow: Water level

Description: Water level

Forcing type: Time Series

Vertical interpolation type:

Reflection parameter:

Thatcher-Harleman time lag: 00:00:00

Factor: 1.00 [-] Offset: 0.00 m

Location

Support point: Boundary01_0001, Boundary01_0002

Geometry

Generate series... Import from files... Export to files... Combined BC view

No data defined, to create boundary data, activate a support point.

Generate time series...

Generate new (selected) / Modify existing

Time range

Start: 4/ 4/2023 12:00:00 AM

End: 4/ 4/2023 2:30:00 AM

Timestep: 0 days, 0 hours, 30 min, 0 sec

Messages

Message	Time
Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

① 新增點位2時序列

② 設定起迄、間隔時間

新增邊界條件

The screenshot shows the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The main window displays the 'Boundary Condition' dialog for 'Boundary01'. The 'Flow' dropdown is set to 'Water level'. The 'Description' field contains 'Boundary01-Water level'. The 'Forcing type' is 'Time Series'. The 'Location' dialog is open, showing 'Support point' with 'Boundary01_0001' and 'Boundary01_0002' selected. The 'Geometry' panel shows a line segment with a red dot at the start and a blue dot at the end. A 'Choose support points' dialog is overlaid on the main window, with the 'OK' button highlighted by a red box and an arrow pointing to it. The text '點擊確認' (Click to confirm) is written below the arrow. The 'Messages' panel at the bottom shows a list of system messages.

Boundary Condition

Flow: Water level

Description: Boundary01-Water level

Forcing type: Time Series

Vertical interpolation type:

Reflection parameter:

Thatcher-Harleman time lag: 00:00:00

Factor: 1.00 [-] Offset: 0.00 m

Location

Support point: Boundary01_0001, Boundary01_0002

Geometry

Choose support points

Apply operation to:

- Selected support point
- Active support points
- Inactive support points
- All support points

OK Cancel

點擊確認

Messages

Message	Time
Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj	2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output	2023-04-04 00:55:05.805
Project Project1 saved	2023-04-04 00:55:05.682
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 00:55:05.118

新增邊界條件

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The main window is titled "Boundary01 (Boundary conditions)". The "Flow" dropdown is set to "Water level". The "Description" field contains "Boundary01-Water level". The "Forcing type" is set to "Time Series". The "Vertical interpolation type" is set to "None". The "Reflection parameter" is set to "None". The "Thatcher-Harleman time lag" is set to "00:00:00". The "Factor" is set to "1.00" and the "Offset" is set to "0.00" m.

The "Location" panel shows two support points: "Boundary01_0001" and "Boundary01_0002". The "Geometry" panel shows a horizontal line segment with a red dot at the start and a blue dot at the end.

The "Properties" panel shows a table with the following data:

Time [-]	WaterLevel [m]
2023/04/04 00:00:00	1.5
2023/04/04 00:30:00	1.5
2023/04/04 01:00:00	1.5
2023/04/04 01:30:00	1.5
2023/04/04 02:00:00	1.5
2023/04/04 02:30:00	1.5

The chart below the table shows a horizontal red line at 1.5 m on the y-axis, representing the water level over time. The x-axis is labeled "Time [-]" and ranges from 00:00 to 02:30. The legend indicates "WaterLevel [m]".

An arrow points to the second row of the table, with the text "編輯點位2水位時序列" (Edit point 2 water level time series).

The "Messages" panel at the bottom shows several messages, including "Project Project1 saved" and "Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj".

新增邊界條件

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a yellow grid overlay. A red box highlights a specific area on the map, which is magnified in a larger inset view on the right. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar with various GIS and simulation tools, and a Project tree on the left. The Project tree shows a hierarchy of elements: Project1, FM_model, General, 1D, 2D, Area, Grid, Bed Level, Initial Conditions, Boundary Conditions, Boundary01, Physical Parameters, Sources and Sinks, 1D2D Links, and Output. The Properties panel on the right shows the selected element's properties, including Area, Unstructured Grid, Bed Level, Initial Water Level, Boundary Conditions, Boundaries, Roughness, Viscosity, and Diffusivity. The Messages panel at the bottom shows a list of system messages, including project saving and model running status.

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid

FM Region 1D2D Links Decorations Tools Edit Grid Profile Backgrou... Network Area Region Network Coverage

Project1 FM_model X Boundary01 (Boundary conditions)

Project1
FM_model
General
1D
2D
Area
Grid
Bed Level
Initial Conditions
Boundary Conditions
Boundary01
Physical Parameters
Sources and Sinks
1D2D Links
Output

Properties

Messages

- Project Project1 saved
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsjproj
- Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsjproj saved
- Project Project1 saved
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsjproj
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output

2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
2023-04-04 00:55:05.805

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

編輯模式設定 (Time Frame)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) software interface. The main window is titled "Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)". The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar, and a project tree on the left. The "Time Frame" settings are highlighted in the center, showing the following parameters:

- Max Courant nr: 0.7
- Reference date: 2023-04-04 00:00:00
- Time zone: 0
- User time step: 0d 00: 01: 00.000
- Max. time step (s): 30
- Initial time step (s): 1
- Update interval for time dep roughness (s): 86400
- Start Time: 2023-04-04 00:00:00
- Stop Time: 2023-04-04 02:30:00

Two red arrows point from the "Time Frame" settings to the "Time step analysis" panel, which contains the following options:

- Autotimestep exclude structure links:
- Exclude negative qin:

The "Messages" panel at the bottom shows a list of system messages, including "Project Project1 saved" and "Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj".

編輯模式設定 (Initial Conditions)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) software interface. The main window is titled "Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)". The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar with various icons, and a project tree on the left. The project tree shows a hierarchy: Project1 > FM_model > General > 1D > Initial Conditions > Boundary01 > Physical Parameters > Sources and Sinks > 1D2D Links > Output.

The main workspace is divided into several panes. The top pane shows the "Initial Conditions" settings for "Boundary01 (Boundary conditions)". It contains three sub-panels: "Initial conditions (1D)", "Initial conditions (2D)", and "Rest file". The "Initial conditions (1D)" panel is highlighted with a red box and has a red arrow pointing to it. The "Initial conditions (2D)" panel is also highlighted with a red box and has a red arrow pointing to it. The "Rest file" panel is highlighted with a red box and has a red arrow pointing to it.

The "Initial conditions (1D)" panel has the following settings:

- Quantity: Water level
- Value: -2

The "Initial conditions (2D)" panel has the following settings:

- Quantity: Water level
- Value: 0

The "Rest file" panel has a "Rest file" input field.

The bottom pane shows the "Messages" window, which contains a list of messages:

- Project Project1 saved (2023-04-04 01:36:29.319)
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj (2023-04-04 01:36:23.550)
- Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved (2023-04-04 00:55:24.180)
- Project Project1 saved (2023-04-04 00:55:24.101)
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj (2023-04-04 00:55:21.365)
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output (2023-04-04 00:55:05.805)

編輯模式設定 (Output Parameters)

The screenshot displays the 'Output Parameters' settings in the Delft3D FM Suite. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar with various icons, and a project tree on the left. The main settings area is divided into two columns of parameters, each with a toggle switch and a text input field. A red arrow points from the top right of the panel to the 'Write Map file' toggle. A white box highlights the 'Write His File' and 'Write Map file' sections, with red lines pointing to the 'His output Interval' and 'Map output interval' input fields.

Parameter	Toggle	Value
Write His File	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
His output Interval	<input type="text"/>	0d 00:05:00.000
Specify His output start time	<input type="checkbox"/>	
His output start time	<input type="text"/>	2023-04-04 00:00:00
Specify His output stop time	<input type="checkbox"/>	
His output stop time	<input type="text"/>	2023-04-04 02:30:00
Write mass balance totals	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write sources-sinks statistics	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write general structure parameters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write orifice parameters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write bridge parameters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write culvert parameters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write dam break parameters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write universal weir parameters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write compound structure parameters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write k eps and vicw	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Write wind velocities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write precipitation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write temperature	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write heat fluxes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write Map file	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Map output interval	<input type="text"/>	0d 00:05:00.000
Specify Map output start time	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Map output start time	<input type="text"/>	2023-04-04 00:00:00
Specify Map output stop time	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Map output stop time	<input type="text"/>	2023-04-04 02:30:00
Write water levels of previous time step	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write water levels	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write flow density	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Write horizontal viscosity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write horizontal diffusivity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write flow flux	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write the number of times a cell was Courant limiting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write the shear stress	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Write the Chezy roughness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write vicw k and eps	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Write wind velocities	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write cumulative water on ground time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Write freeboard	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Messages:

- Project Project1 saved
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj
- Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved
- Project Project1 saved
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output

模式設定檢查 (Validation)

模式設定檢查 (Validation)

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Configure DIMR Logfile loglevel: None
Configure DIMR userfeedback loglevel: None

Project: Project1

- FM_model (Water Flow FM Model)
- SedimentThickness
- Model Coordinate System
- Computational grid
- Network
- Links
- Bathymetry
- Physical Processes
- Roughness
- Water flow FM model wind forcing
- Water flow FM model meteo items
- WaterFlow FM model definition
- Water flow FM model boundary conditions
- Structures
- Initial Conditions
- Embankment definitions
- Enclosure
- HydroLinks

FM_model (Water Flow FM Model)

- SedimentThickness
- Model Coordinate System
- Computational grid
- Network
- Links
- Bathymetry
- Physical Processes
- Roughness
- Water flow FM model wind forcing
- Water flow FM model meteo items
- WaterFlow FM model definition
- Water flow FM model boundary conditions
- Structures
- Initial Conditions
- Embankment definitions
- Enclosure
- HydroLinks

綠色代表通過檢查

Messages

- Project Project1 saved 2023-04-04 01:36:29.319
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj 2023-04-04 01:36:23.550
- Project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj saved 2023-04-04 00:55:24.180
- Project Project1 saved 2023-04-04 00:55:24.101
- Saving project Project1 as E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\Project1.dsproj 2023-04-04 00:55:21.365
- Running this model requires the OutputDirectory to be overwritten to: output 2023-04-04 00:55:05.805

Validate before run

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

調整檢視範圍

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a yellow grid overlay. A red box highlights the 'Zoom Previous' and 'Zoom to map extent' buttons in the toolbar. A callout box with the Chinese characters '點選' (Click) points to these buttons. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, Spatial Operations, Grid, Config, DIMR), a toolbar with various navigation and editing tools, a project tree on the left, a properties panel on the bottom left, and a messages panel at the bottom.

Map navigation tools highlighted:

- Zoom Previous
- Zoom to map extent

Properties Panel (Network):

- Name: network
- BranchCount: 0
- NodeCount: 0
- CoordinateSystem: Amersfoort / RD New

Messages Panel:

Icon	Message	Time
Info	Wall clock "FM_model": Start time: 04-Apr-2023 01:48:20.	2023-04-04 01:48:21.766
Info	Model "FM_model" has finished in 150 steps.	2023-04-04 01:48:21.766
Info	Wall clock "FM_model": Start time: 04-Apr-2023 01:47:58.	2023-04-04 01:47:58.859
Info	Model "FM_model" has finished in 150 steps.	2023-04-04 01:47:58.859

選取觀測結果 (以水深為例)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a yellow grid overlay. The software interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a ribbon with various tool groups (Map, Spatial Operations, Grid, Config, DIMR), and a project tree on the left. The project tree shows the following structure:

- Project1
 - FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundary01
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Output
 - Dimr Run Log
 - FM_model.dia
 - water_balance_total_volume
 - water_balance_storage
 - water_balance_volume_error

The Properties panel on the right is open to the 'Map' tab. The 'Output' section is expanded, and the following items are listed:

- Output
 - Map File 2D
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Number of times flow element was Courant limiting (Mesh2d_Num)
 - Water level (Mesh2d_sl)
 - Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)
 - Velocity at velocity point, n-component (Mesh2d_u1)
 - Flow element center velocity vector, x-component (Mesh2d_uvx)
 - Flow element center velocity vector, y-component (Mesh2d_uvy)
 - Flow element center velocity magnitude (Mesh2d_ucmag)
 - Discharge through flow link at current time (Mesh2d_q1)
 - velocity (ucx + ucy)
 - His File

The 'Map' tab is selected, and the 'Map' button in the bottom right corner is highlighted with a red circle. The 'Output' section is highlighted with a red box, and the 'Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)' item is highlighted with a red circle. A red circle labeled '2' is also present near the 'Map' tab. A red circle labeled '3' is present near the 'Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)' item. A red box labeled '勾選' (checked) is positioned near the 'Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)' item.

The Messages panel at the bottom shows the following log entries:

Message	Time
Wall clock "FM_model": Start time: 04-Apr-2023 01:48:20.	2023-04-04 01:48:21.766
Model "FM_model" has finished in 150 steps.	2023-04-04 01:48:21.766
Wall clock "FM_model": Start time: 04-Apr-2023 01:47:58.	2023-04-04 01:47:58.859
Model "FM_model" has finished in 150 steps.	2023-04-04 01:47:58.859

播放淹水動畫

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a grid overlay representing the simulation domain. The grid is color-coded, with blue representing low water levels and yellow/green representing higher water levels, indicating the progression of a flood event. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a ribbon with various tool groups (Map, Spatial Operations, Grid, DIMR), and several panels:

- Project Panel:** Lists the project structure, including FM_model, General, 1D, 2D, Area, Grid, Bed Level, Initial Conditions, Boundary Conditions, Physical Parameters, Sources and Sinks, 1D/2D Links, and Output.
- Properties Panel:** Shows settings for the selected grid layer, including coordinates (Amersfoort / RD New), general settings (Opacity: 0.8), and rendering options (RenderMode: Flat, HardwareOpenTK).
- Map Panel:** Contains a list of layers and their visibility settings. Key settings include:
 - FM_model: checked
 - 1D: checked
 - 2D: checked
 - Area: checked
 - Unstructured Grid: checked
 - Bed Level: unchecked
 - Initial Water Level: unchecked
 - Boundary Conditions: checked
 - Boundaries: checked
 - Roughness: unchecked
 - Viscosity: unchecked
 - Diffusivity: unchecked
 - Infiltration: unchecked
 - Sources and Sinks: checked
 - 1D/2D Links: checked
 - Estimated Grid-snapped Features: unchecked
 - Output: checked
 - Map File 2D: checked
 - Unstructured Grid: checked
 - Number of times flow element was Courant limiting (Mesh2d_Num): unchecked
 - Water level (Mesh2d_s1): unchecked
 - Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth): checked**
 - Velocity at velocity point, n-component (Mesh2d_u1): unchecked
 - Flow element center velocity vector, x-component (Mesh2d_ucx): unchecked
 - Flow element center velocity vector, y-component (Mesh2d_uci): unchecked
 - Flow element center velocity magnitude (Mesh2d_ucmag): unchecked
 - Discharge through flow link at current time (Mesh2d_q1): unchecked
 - Velocity (ucx + ucy): unchecked
 - His File: checked
 - BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS: checked
 - standaard: checked
 - grijs: unchecked
 - pastel: unchecked
 - water: unchecked

At the bottom of the interface, the **Time Navigator** panel is visible. It shows a timeline from 00:00:00.000 to 02:30:00.000 on 04/04/2023 01:40:00. A red vertical line indicates the current simulation time, which is approximately 01:45:00.000. The Time Navigator panel includes playback controls (play, stop, previous, next) and a delay setting of 0.1 sec. Two red circles with numbers 1 and 2 are overlaid on the interface: circle 1 points to the 'Time Navigator' label, and circle 2 points to the play button.

修改水深顯示色彩

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a grid overlay representing water depth. The map is color-coded, with blue representing lower depths and yellow/green representing higher depths. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a toolbar with various GIS and simulation tools, and a project tree on the left. The right-hand side features a 'Map' panel with a legend for the 'FM_model' layer. The legend is expanded to show the 'Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)' layer, which has a color scale ranging from 0 (blue) to 1.215 (red). A context menu is open over the legend, with two red arrows pointing to the 'Legend Properties' option. The first arrow is labeled '1 右鍵展開選單' (Right-click to expand menu) and the second is labeled '2 點選' (Click). The bottom of the interface shows a 'Time Navigator' panel with a timeline and a 'RenderMode' panel.

① 右鍵展開選單

② 點選

修改水深顯示色彩

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) software interface. The main window shows a map of a water body with a grid overlay. The 'Properties' dialog box is open, showing the 'Mesh2d_waterdepth' feature attribute and a color scale. The 'Color scale' dropdown is highlighted with a red circle and arrow labeled '1'. The 'Generate' button is highlighted with a red circle and arrow labeled '2'. The 'Apply' button is highlighted with a red circle and arrow labeled '3'.

The 'Properties' dialog box shows the following settings:

- Theme: Gradient theme
- Feature attribute: Mesh2d_waterdepth
- Color scale: [Dropdown menu]
- Number of classes: 12
- Auto scale: [Selected]
- Custom range: min: 0, max: 0
- No data value: -999

The 'Generate' button is highlighted with a red circle and arrow labeled '2'. The 'Apply' button is highlighted with a red circle and arrow labeled '3'.

Value	Min	Max	Symbol	Label
1.215			■	1.215
1.104			■	1.104
0.9937			■	0.9937
0.8833			■	0.8833
0.7729			■	0.7729
0.6625			■	0.6625
0.5521			■	0.5521
0.4417			■	0.4417
0.3312			■	0.3312
0.2208			■	0.2208
0.1104			■	0.1104
0			■	0

播放淹水動畫

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a yellow grid overlay, representing the simulation domain. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a ribbon with various tool groups (Map, Spatial Operations, Grid, DIMR), and a toolbar. The Project Explorer on the left shows the project structure, including the FM_model and its various layers and settings. The Properties panel on the left shows the Grid layer settings, including coordinates and rendering options. The Time Navigator at the bottom shows a timeline from 00:00:00.000 to 02:30:00.000 (2023-04-04) with a play button and a red vertical line indicating the current time. A red circle with the number '2' highlights the play button, and a red circle with the number '1' highlights the 'Time Navigator' label.

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Map

FM_model X Boundary01 (Boundary conditions) FM_model (FM model settings) FM_model

Map

Map

FM_model

1D

2D

Area

Unstructured Grid

Bed Level

Initial Water Level

Boundary Conditions

Boundaries

Roughness

Viscosity

Diffusivity

Infiltration

Sources and Sinks

1D/2D Links

Estimated Grid-snapped Features

Output

Map File 2D

Unstructured Grid

Number of times flow element was Courant limiting (Mesh2d_N)

Water level (Mesh2d_s1)

Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)

1.215

1.104

0.9937

0.8833

0.7729

0.6625

0.5521

0.4417

0.3312

0.2208

0.1104

0

Velocity at velocity point, n-component (Mesh2d_u1)

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

Time Navigator

04/04/2023 01:04:55

Delay: 0.1 sec

00:00:00.000 00:15:00.000 00:30:00.000 00:45:00.000 01:00:00.000 01:15:00.000 01:30:00.000 01:45:00.000 02:00:00.000 02:15:00.000 02:30:00.000

(2023-04-04)

Time Navigator

加入水位觀測點

1 選取新增觀測點功能

2 放置觀測點

3 重新執行模擬

Coordinate system: "Amersfoort / RD New" (EPSG: 28992) - Current map coordinates: 123224.18210075, 472645.117339065

檢視觀測點水位時序序列

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The main map area shows a yellow grid overlaid on a water body. A context menu is open over the grid, with two red arrows pointing to specific options: '右鍵開啟選單' (Right-click to open menu) pointing to the context menu itself, and '放置觀測點' (Place observation point) pointing to the 'Query time series' option. The 'Time Navigator' at the bottom shows a time series plot with a vertical red line indicating the current time, and a scale from 00:00:00.000 to 02:30:00.000. The plot shows a series of green dots representing data points over time.

右鍵開啟選單

放置觀測點

檢視觀測點水位時序列

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a grid overlay. A dialog box titled "Select Time Dependent Spatial Data" is open, listing available items. The item "FM_model water depth (waterdepth)" is selected and highlighted in blue. A red circle with the number "1" points to this selection. A red circle with the number "2" points to the "OK" button in the dialog box. A text box with the Chinese characters "確認" (Confirm) is next to the "OK" button. Another text box with the Chinese characters "選取觀測參數 (以水深為例)" (Select observation parameter (example: water depth)) is positioned above the dialog box. The interface also shows a project tree on the left, a properties panel at the bottom left, and a time navigator at the bottom center. The time navigator shows a timeline from 00:00:00.000 to 02:30:00.000 on 2023-04-04, with a vertical line indicating the current time.

選取觀測參數
(以水深為例)

1

2 確認

OK

Cancel

Available items

Overaar	SpatialData
FM_model	water level (waterlevel)
FM_model	water depth (waterdepth)
FM_model	Total bed shear stress (tau)
FM_model	flow element center velocity vector, x-component (x_velocity)
FM_model	flow element center velocity vector, y-component (y_velocity)
FM_model	velocity magnitude (velocity_magnitude)
FM_model	average discharge magnitude (discharge_magnitude)
FM_model	Mean bed shear stress (wtau)

Time Navigator

04/04/2023 00:50:00

Delay: 0.1 sec

00:00:00.000 00:15:00.000 00:30:00.000 00:45:00.000 01:00:00.000 01:15:00.000 01:30:00.000 01:45:00.000 02:00:00.000 02:15:00.000 02:30:00.000

(2023-04-04)

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

檢視觀測點水位時序列

一二維 耦合模式

0. 基於二維模式建模成果

1. 新增渠道

(1) 繪製渠道路徑

(2) 新增渠道斷面

(3) 新增計算結點

2. 新增下水道

(1) 繪製下水道管線

(2) 編輯下水道斷面

3. 建立一、二維連結(Links)

4. 執行模擬

5. 檢視模擬成果

調整檢示範圍

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map of a coastal area with a yellow grid overlay. A red rectangular box highlights a specific region on the grid, labeled with a circled '2' and the text '框選欲放大之區域' (Select the area to be zoomed in). The software's menu bar includes File, Home, View, Tools, Map, Spatial Operations, Grid, and Config. The toolbar contains various icons for map navigation and analysis. The left sidebar shows a project tree with folders for '1D' and '2D' models. The right sidebar shows a layer list with various model parameters. The bottom of the interface includes a Time Navigator and a Messages panel.

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Map

Zoom Previous Zoom Next Map Coordinate System Export As Image Show Profile Add dutch layers

Scale Bar Query Features Query Time Series

Decorations Tools Edit Grid Profile Background... Network Area Region Network Coverage

Project

FM_model Boundary01 (Boundary conditions) FM_model (FM model settings) FM_model water depth (waterdepth) at ObservationPoint_2D_01

Map

Use focused layer

Map

- FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped Features
 - Output
 - BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS
 - standaard
 - grijs
 - pastel
 - water

Properties

Network

General

Name network

BranchCount 0

NodeCount 0

Misc

CoordinateSystem Amersfoort / RD New

Name

Name of network.

Time Navigator

01/01/0001 00:00:00

Delay: 0.1 sec

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

2 框選欲放大之區域

新增一維渠道

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Generate links North Arrow Zoom Previous Map Coordinate System Show Profile Add dutch layers (1) Network Coverage Add Route Show Side View

Embedded 1-to-1 Legend Zoom Next Export As Image Query Features Query Time Series

Decorations Tools Edit Grid Profile Background Network Area Region Network Coverage

Project FM_model X Boundary01 (Boundary conditions) FM_model (FM model settings) FM_model Validation Report

Project1
FM_model
General
1D
network
Computational 1D Grid
1D Roughness
1D Initial Conditions
1D Boundary Conditions
Lateral Sources
2D
Area
Grid
Bed Level
Initial Conditions
Boundary Conditions
Boundary01
Physical Parameters
Sources and Sinks
1D2D Links
Output

Channel
General
Name Channel_ID_1
Long name
Has custom length False
Length 973.22
Geometry length 973.64
Geodetic length 973.22
Order number -1
Attributes (0 attributes)
Relations
From node Node001
To node Node002
Branch Features
Number of cross-sec 0
Number of cross-sec 0

Attributes
All the (custom) attributes for this object.

Map
Map
FM_model
1D
2D
Area
Unstructured Grid
Bed Level
Initial Water Level
Boundary Conditions
Boundaries
Roughness
Viscosity
Diffusivity
Infiltration
Sources and Sinks
1D/2D Links
Estimated Grid-snapped Features
BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS
standaard
grijs
pastel
water

Time Navigator
01/01/0001 000000
Delay: 0.1 sec

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

雙擊結束繪製

單擊新增結點

單擊新增結點

單擊開始繪製 (2)

新增渠道断面

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map of a river network with a yellow grid overlay. A blue line represents a cross-section across a channel. Three red circles and arrows indicate key actions:

- ①: A red circle highlights a tool in the toolbar, likely used for adding or editing cross-sections.
- ②: A red circle and arrow point to a new cross-section point being added to the channel.
- ③: A red circle and arrow point to an existing cross-section point, with the text "雙擊編輯断面" (Double-click to edit cross-section) next to it.

The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, Spatial Operations, Grid, Config, DIMR), a toolbar with various GIS tools, a project tree on the left, a map view in the center, and a properties panel on the right. The properties panel shows details for the selected cross-section, including its name, long name, attributes, administration, definition, and metrics.

編輯斷面資料

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Configure DIMR logfile loglevel: None
Configure DIMR userfeedback loglevel: None

Project: FM_model, Boundary01 (Boundary conditions), FM_model (FM model settings), FM_model Validation Report, CrossSection_ID_1 X

Map: Use focused layer

ZW Table

Z	Width	Storage width
0	26	0
-2	20	0
*		

Profile 'CrossSection_ID_1'

Z (m) vs Offset (m) graph showing Flow profile (green), Total profile (blue), and Storage Area (0 m²) (yellow). The graph shows a trapezoidal cross-section with a main channel at Z=0 and a floodplain at Z=-2.

Section Widths

Section	Width (m)
Main	26.000
FloodPlain1	0.000
FloodPlain2	0.000

Definition

Cross section type: ZW
Thalweg: 0

Metrics

Lowest point: -2
Highest point: 0

Name

Id of the cross section:

Chainage: 469.36669663547542
Floodplain base level: 0.00 m

Time Navigator

Messages | Time Navigator | Chart | Region | Map | Operations | Toolbox

新增渠道計算結點 (Computational Grid Nodes)

1 點選渠道、右鍵開啟選單

2 點選開啟編輯界面

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Generate links Add link Embedded 1-to-1 FM Region 1D2D Links Decorations Tools Query Features Query Time Series Edit Grid Profile Background Network Area Region Network Coverage Add Route Show Side View

Project1 FM_model Boundary01 (Boundary conditions) FM_model (FM model settings) FM_model Validation Report CrossSection_1D_1

Project1 FM_model General network Computational 1D Grid 1D Roughness 1D Initial Conditions 1D Boundary Conditions Lateral Sources 2D Area Grid Bed Level Initial Conditions Boundary Conditions Boundary01 Physical Parameters Sources and Sinks 1D2D Links Output

Channel

General Name Channel_ID_1 Long name Has custom length False Length 973.22 Geometry length 973.64 Geodetic length 973.22 Order number -1 Attributes (0 attributes)

Relations From node Node001 To node Node002

Branch Features Number of cross-sec 1

Attributes All the (custom) attributes for this object.

Time Navigator 01/01/0001 00:00:00 Delay: 0.1 sec

Messages Time Navigator Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

新增渠道計算結點 (Computational Grid Nodes)

Generate Computational Grid

Create segments for:

- All branches
- Selected branches

If branch already has grid points:

- Generate new grid points
- Use existing grid points

Positions:

- None (Remove grid from branch)
- Preferred length: 100 m
- Special locations:
 - Cross Section
 - Lateral Sources
 - Structure

Minimum cell length: 0.5 m

勾選 設定結點距離100m

Channel

General

Name: Channel_ID_1

Long name

Has custom length: False

Length: 973.22

Geometry length: 973.64

Geodetic length: 973.22

Order number: -1

Attributes: (0 attributes)

Relations

From node: Node001

To node: Node002

Branch Features

Number of cross-sec: 1

Attributes

All the (custom) attributes for this object.

渠道新增成果

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a 2D model of a waterway network with a newly added channel highlighted in blue. The channel is labeled "Proostdijerdersloot" and connects to "Proostdijerderschuit" and "Proostdijerdersloot". The model includes a yellow grid and various waterway features like "Botsholse dwarsweg", "Proostdijerdersweg", and "Hooftweg".

The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools), a ribbon with various toolsets (Map, Spatial Operations, Grid, Config, DIMR), and a toolbar. The left sidebar shows the Project tree with folders for 1D and 2D models. The right sidebar shows the Map legend with various layers and styles. The bottom panel shows the Time Navigator and Properties panel for the selected channel.

Properties Panel:

- Channel: Channel_ID_1
- General
 - Name: Channel_ID_1
 - Long name:
 - Has custom length: False
 - Length: 973.22
 - Geometry length: 973.64
 - Geodetic length: 973.22
 - Order number: -1
 - Attributes: (0 attributes)
- Relations
 - From node: Node001
 - To node: Node002
- Branch Features
 - Number of cross-sec 1
 - Number of cross-section 0
- Attributes
 - All the (custom) attributes for this object.

Map Legend:

- FM_model
 - 1D
 - Computational 1D Grid
 - 1D Roughness
 - 1D Initial Conditions
 - 1D Boundary Conditions
 - Lateral Sources
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundary01
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Output
- BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS
 - standaard
 - grijs
 - pastel
 - water

新增下水道系統

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools GIS Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Generate links Add link Scale Bar North Arrow Legend Query Features Zoom Previous Zoom Next Export As Image Map Coordinate System Show Profile Add dutch layers Network Area Region Link Coverage Computational 1D Grid Add Route Show Side View

Project1

- FM_model
 - General
 - 1D
 - network
 - Computational 1D Grid
 - 1D Roughness
 - 1D Initial Conditions
 - 1D Boundary Conditions
 - Lateral Sources
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundary01
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output

Properties

SewerConnectionProperties

General

- Name: Pipe_1D.3
- Length: 323.9
- Geometry length: 323.9
- Invert level begin (m): -2
- Invert level end (m): -2
- Water type: Combined
- Order number: -1

Relations

- From manhole: Manhole003
- To manhole: Manhole004
- From compartment: Compartment003
- To compartment: Compartment004

Cross Section

- Name: Default Pipe Profile

Map

- FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped Features
- BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS
 - standaard
 - grijs
 - pastel
 - water

Time Navigator

01/01/0001 000000

Delay: 0.1 sec

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

雙擊完成繪製

單擊開始繪製

單擊完成繪製

單擊開始繪製

單擊完成繪製

單擊開始繪製

1

2

新增下水道系統

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Generate links Add link Embedded 1-to-1 1D2D Links

North Arrow Legend Scale Bar

Zoom Previous Zoom Next Query Features Query Time Series

Map Coordinate System Show Profile Add dutch layers

Link Coverage Computational 1D Grid Add Route Show Side View

FM Region 1D2D Links Decorations Tools Edit Grid Profile Background... Network Area Region Network Coverage

Project FM_model X Boundary01 (Boundary conditions) FM_model (FM model settings) FM_model Validation Report CrossSection_ID_1

Project1 FM_model General 1D network Computational 1D Grid 1D Roughness 1D Initial Conditions 1D Boundary Conditions Lateral Sources 2D Area Grid Bed Level Initial Conditions Boundary Conditions Physical Parameters Sources and Sinks 1D2D Links Output

Properties SewerConnectionProperties

General Name Pipe_1D_3 Length 323.9 Geometry length 323.9 Invert level begin (m) -2 Invert level end (m) -2 Water type Combined Order number -1

Relations From manhole Manhole003 To manhole Manhole004 From compartment Compartment003 To compartment Compartment004

Cross Section Name Default Pipe Profile

Map

Map FM_model 1D 2D Area Unstructured Grid Bed Level Initial Water Level Boundary Conditions Boundaries Roughness Viscosity Diffusivity Infiltration Sources and Sinks 1D/2D Links Estimated Grid-snapped Features BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS standaard grijs pastel water

Time Navigator

01/01/0001 000000

Delay: 0.1 sec

Messages Time Navigator

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

雙擊開啟下水道編輯介面

新增下水道系統

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface for configuring a sewer system. The main window shows the configuration for a pipe named 'Pipe_1D_2'.

General info

- Name: Pipe_1D_2
- Type: Combined
- Length [m]: 328.9
- Slope [deg]: 0
- Material: Concrete
- Roughness: 0.003
- Roughness type: WhiteColebrook

Connections and levels

	Begin node	End node
Manhole ID	Manhole002	Manhole003
Compartment ID	Compartment002	Compartment003
Invert level [m]	-2	-2

Cross section

Type: Circle
Diameter: 0.400 m

The cross-section diagram shows a circular pipe profile with a diameter of 0.400 m. The vertical axis is labeled 'Z (m)' and ranges from -0.05 to 0.4. The horizontal axis is labeled 'Offset (m)' and ranges from -0.2 to 0.2. The pipe is centered at Z=0. A legend indicates 'Flow profile'.

Properties

SewerConnectionProperties

General

- Name: Pipe_1D_2
- Length: 328.9
- Geometry length: 328.9
- Invert level begin (m): -2
- Invert level end (m): -2
- Water type: Combined
- Order number: -1

Relations

- From manhole: Manhole002
- To manhole: Manhole003
- From compartment: Compartment002
- To compartment: Compartment003

Cross Section

- Name: Default Pipe Profile

Table

Start	End	Roughness
0.00	0.40	Sewer

Time Navigator

Record 1 of 1

新增一二維連結(Links)

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

File Home View Tools Map GIS Spatial Operations Grid Config DIMR

Generate links Add link Scale Bar

1 2

雙擊結束繪製

單擊開始繪製

單擊新增結點

單擊新增結點

單擊新增結點

Time Navigator

04/04/2023 00:00:00

Delay: 0.1 sec

00:00:00.000 00:15:00.000 00:30:00.000 00:45:00.000 01:00:00.000 01:15:00.000 01:30:00.000 01:45:00.000 02:00:00.000 02:15:00.000 02:30:00.000

(2023-04-04)

Messages Time Navigator

Coordinate system: "Amersfoort / RD New" (EPSG: 28992) - Current map coordinates: 121998.292760337, 472597.705139383

Map

- FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped Features
 - Output
 - Map File 1D
 - Map File 2D
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Number of times flow element was Courant limiting (Mesh2d_N)
 - Water level (Mesh2d_s1)
 - Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)
 - Velocity at velocity point, n-component (Mesh2d_u1)
 - Flow element center velocity vector, x-component (Mesh2d_ucx)
 - Flow element center velocity vector, y-component (Mesh2d_ucy)
 - Flow element center velocity magnitude (Mesh2d_ucmag)
 - Discharge through flow link at current time (Mesh2d_q1)
 - velocity (ucx + ucy)
 - His File

- BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS
- standaard
- grijs
- pastel

新增一二維連結(Links)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) software interface. The main window shows a map view of a river network with a yellow grid overlay. Two vertical links are highlighted: a blue link on the left and a black link on the right, both connecting a 1D channel to a 2D area. The interface includes a top menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, GIS, Config, DIMR), a toolbar with various GIS and model tools, and a right-hand panel with a 'Map' section containing a tree view of the model's layers and properties. The 'Map' section is expanded to show the '2D' layer, which includes 'Area', 'Grid', 'Bed Level', 'Initial Conditions', 'Boundary Conditions', 'Physical Parameters', and 'Sources and Sinks'. The '1D/2D Links' option is checked. The 'Output' section is also expanded, showing various simulation results like 'Map File 1D', 'Map File 2D', 'Unstructured Grid', 'Water level', 'Water depth', 'Velocity', 'Flow element center velocity vector', 'Discharge through flow link at current time', and 'His File'. The 'BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS' is also checked, with 'standaard' selected. At the bottom, there is a 'Time Navigator' panel showing a timeline from 00:00:00.000 to 02:30:00.000 (2023-04-04) with a 'Delay: 0.1 sec' slider. The 'Messages' and 'Time Navigator' tabs are visible at the bottom left.

模式設定檢查 (Validation)

模式設定檢查 (Validation)

Project1 - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)

Configure DIMR logfile loglevel: None
Configure DIMR userfeedback loglevel: None

Project: Project1

- FM_model (Water Flow FM Model)
 - ✓ SedimentThickness
 - ✓ Model Coordinate System
 - ✓ Computational grid
 - ✓ Network
 - ✓ Links
 - ✓ Bathymetry
 - ✓ Physical Processes
 - ✓ Roughness
 - ✓ Water flow FM model wind forcing
 - ✓ Water flow FM model meteo items
 - ✓ WaterFlow FM model definition
 - ✓ Water flow FM model boundary conditions
 - ✓ Structures
 - ✓ Initial Conditions
 - ✓ Embankment definitions
 - ✓ Enclosure
 - ✓ Hydrolinks

Properties: WaterFlowFMMModel

Run mode

- Validate before run: True
- Show model run con: False
- Use RPC: True

Validate before run

Time Navigator

Messages | Time Navigator

Chart | Region | Map | Operations | Toolbox

綠色代表通過檢查

新增觀測路徑 (route_1)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface for creating a new observation route. The main map area shows a grid with a blue route labeled 'route_1' overlaid. The route starts at a point marked with a green circle and ends at a point marked with a blue circle. Red arrows and callouts indicate the steps:

- 1. Clicking 'Add Route' in the 'Coverage' dropdown menu.
- 2. Clicking the start point of the route on the map.
- 3. Clicking the end point of the route on the map.

The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map, GIS, Config), toolbars for map operations and network management, a project tree on the left, a central map area with a grid and a blue route, and a properties panel on the right. The 'Coverage' dropdown menu is highlighted, showing 'Add Route' and 'Show Side View' options. The 'Add Route' option is circled in red. The 'Coverage' dropdown is also highlighted with a red box. The 'Add Route' button is also highlighted with a red box. The 'Show Side View' button is also highlighted with a red box. The 'Coverage' dropdown is also highlighted with a red box. The 'Add Route' button is also highlighted with a red box. The 'Show Side View' button is also highlighted with a red box.

新增觀測路徑 (route_2)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) software interface. The main window shows a map view with a grid overlay. A red box highlights the 'Add Route' button in the 'Coverage route_2' dropdown menu. Red arrows point to the start and end points of the route on the map, labeled '單擊開始繪製' (Click to start drawing) and '單擊結束繪製' (Click to end drawing) respectively. The 'Properties' panel on the left shows details for 'Pipe_1D_3_323.902'.

Coverage route_2

- Add Route
- Show Side View

單擊開始繪製 (Click to start drawing)

單擊結束繪製 (Click to end drawing)

Properties

Network location

General

Name: Pipe_1D_3_323.902

Long name

Administration

Branch: Pipe_1D_3

Chainage (map): 323.90216861822807

Chainage: 323.90216861822807

Time Navigator

01/01/0001 00:00:00

Delay: 0.1 sec

Messages | **Time Navigator**

Output

- Map File 1D
- Map File 2D
- Unstructured Grid
- 1D/2D Links
- Number of times flow element was Courant limiting (Mesh2d_N)
- Water level (Mesh2d_s1)
- Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)
- Velocity at velocity point, n-component (Mesh2d_u1)
- Flow element center velocity vector, x-component (Mesh2d_u)
- Flow element center velocity vector, y-component (Mesh2d_v)
- Flow element center velocity magnitude (Mesh2d_ucmag)
- Discharge through flow link at current time (Mesh2d_q1)
- Velocity at velocity point, n-component (links_u1)
- Discharge through flow link at current time (links_q1)
- velocity (ucx + ucy)
- His File

BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS

檢視觀測路徑模擬結果 (route_1)

點選檢視模擬結果

- 1D
- 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
 - Viscosity
 - Diffusivity
 - Infiltration
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Estimated Grid-snapped Features
- Output
 - Map File 1D
 - Map File 2D
 - Unstructured Grid
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Number of times flow element was Courant limiting (Mesh2d_n)
 - Water level (Mesh2d_s1)
 - Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)
 - Velocity at velocity point, n-component (Mesh2d_u1)
 - Flow element center velocity vector, x-component (Mesh2d_ux)
 - Flow element center velocity vector, y-component (Mesh2d_uy)
 - Flow element center velocity magnitude (Mesh2d_ucmag)
 - Discharge through flow link at current time (Mesh2d_q1)
 - Velocity at velocity point, n-component (links_u1)
 - Discharge through flow link at current time (links_q1)
 - velocity (ucx + ucy)
 - His File
- BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS

檢視觀測路徑模擬結果 (route_1)

檢視觀測路徑模擬結果 (route_2)

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite software interface. The main window shows a map with a yellow grid and two vertical paths (route_1 and route_2) marked with blue and purple lines and arrows. A 'Coverage' dropdown menu is open, showing 'route_2' selected. A 'Show Side View' button is highlighted with a red box and a circled '2'. A circled '1' is placed over the 'route_2' option in the dropdown. The interface includes a top menu bar, a left sidebar with a project tree, a bottom Time Navigator, and a right sidebar with various simulation parameters.

檢視觀測路徑模擬結果 (route_2)

一二維 耦合模式 (一維邊界條件)

Define Modelling Area |

Load Elevation Data |

Generate Mesh & Interpolate Elevation |

Define Boundary Condition |

Run the Simulation |

View the Modeling Results |

刪除二維邊界條件

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04) software interface. The main window shows a map view with a yellow grid overlaying a blue water body. A context menu is open over a selected grid element, with the 'Delete selection' option highlighted. Red annotations with numbers 1 and 2 point to the right-click and the 'Delete selection' option respectively.

右鍵開啟選單

點選刪除物件

Project Tree (Left):

- Lateral Sources
- 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundary01
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
- 1D2D Links
- Output
 - Dimr Run Log
 - FM_model.dia
 - water_balance_total_volume
 - water_balance_storage
 - water_balance_volume_error
 - water_balance_boundaries_in
 - water_balance_boundaries_out
 - water_balance_boundaries_tota

Properties Panel (Right):

- Map
 - FM_model
 - 1D
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Unstructured Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Water Level
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Boundaries
 - Roughness
- sources and sinks
- 1D/2D Links
- Estimated Grid-snapped Features
- Output
 - Map File 1D
 - Map File 2D
 - Unstructured Grid
 - 1D/2D Links
 - Number of times flow element was Courant limiting (Mesh2d_N
 - Water level (Mesh2d_s1)
 - Water depth at pressure points (Mesh2d_waterdepth)
 - Velocity at velocity point, n-component (Mesh2d_u1)
 - Flow element center velocity vector, x-component (Mesh2d
 - Flow element center velocity vector, y-component (Mesh2d
 - Flow element center velocity magnitude (Mesh2d_ucmag)
 - Discharge through flow link at current time (Mesh2d_q1)
 - Velocity at velocity point, n-component (links_u1)
 - Discharge through flow link at current time (links_q1)
 - velocity (ucx + ucy)
- His File

- BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS

Time Navigator (Bottom):

04/04/2023 01:10:00

Delay: 0.1 sec

00:00:00.000 00:15:00.000 00:30:00.000 00:45:00.000 01:00:00.000 01:15:00.000 01:30:00.000 01:45:00.000 02:00:00.000 02:15:00.000 02:30:00.000

(2023-04-04)

新增一維側入流

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 interface. The main window shows a 2D map with a yellow grid. Two vertical flow paths are visible: a blue path on the left and a red path on the right. Red circles '1', '2', and '3' highlight specific elements: '1' is a tool in the Network toolbar, '2' is a node on the blue path, and '3' is a node on the red path. The interface includes a menu bar (File, Home, View, Tools, Map), toolbars (Spatial Operations, Grid, DIMR, Network, Area, Region), a project tree (1D2D_C, FM_model), a properties panel (Category: General, Index: 517, Type: Cell), a messages log, and a map legend (Map, FM_model, 1D, 2D, BRT Achtergrondkaart WMTS, standaard, grijs, pastel, water). The title bar reads '1D2D_C* - Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 1D2D (2022.04)'. The status bar at the bottom shows 'Chart', 'Region', 'Map', 'Operations', and 'Toolbox'.

設定側入流資料

The screenshot displays the DelR3D FM Suite interface. The main map shows a hydro network with a blue channel and a red lateral source. A context menu is open over a node, with a red box highlighting the 'Node001 (Nodes)' option. The Properties panel on the left shows details for 'selected Hydro node (1)'. The Messages panel at the bottom shows system logs.

框選結點 右鍵開啟選單

1 (Red box around the node)

2 (Red circle around the context menu)

3 (Red circle around the 'Node001 (Nodes)' option in the context menu)

Property	Value
Name	Node001
Long name	
X coordinate	122093.48106348174
Y coordinate	471494.64068528923
Attributes	(0 attributes)
Incoming branches	0
Outgoing branches	1
Is on single branch	True

Message	Time
Network has changed, clearing results.	
Loaded project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\1D2D_C.dsproj	2023-04-04 03:48:26.241
File E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\1D2D_C.dsproj_data\FM_model\in	2023-04-04 03:47:40.248
File E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\1D2D_C.dsproj_data\FM_model\in	2023-04-04 03:47:40.803
File E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\1D2D_C.dsproj_data\FM_model\in	2023-04-04 03:47:40.803
Network has changed, clearing results.	2023-04-04 03:47:39.186
Creating database session ...	2023-04-04 03:47:38.363

設定側入流資料

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite interface. The main window shows the configuration for a lateral source named 'LateralSource_1D_2' with a flow rate of 10 m³/s. A red arrow points from the 'Flow Data' section to a magnified view of the configuration details.

Flow Data Configuration:

- Type: Q : Constant flow
- Flow [m³/s]: 10

Properties Panel (selected Hydro node 1):

- General**
 - Name: Node001
 - Long name: 122093.48106348174
 - X coordinate: 471494.64068528923
 - Y coordinate: (0 attributes)
- Relations**
 - Incoming branches: 0
 - Outgoing branches: 1
 - Is on single branch: True

Messages Panel:

- Network has changed, clearing results. (2023-04-04 03:48:26.241)
- Loaded project E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\1D2D_C.dsproj (2023-04-04 03:47:48.248)
- File E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\1D2D_C.dsproj_data\FM_model\input\FM_model_boundaryconditions1d.bc, block starting at line 13: support point Node002 w (2023-04-04 03:47:40.803)
- File E:\F_MODEL_CASE\DFLOW\DEMO\1D2D_C.dsproj_data\FM_model\input\FM_model_boundaryconditions1d.bc, block starting at line 5: support point Node001 wa (2023-04-04 03:47:40.803)
- Network has changed, clearing results. (2023-04-04 03:47:39.186)
- Creating database session ... (2023-04-04 03:47:38.363)

設定側入流資料

框選結點
右鍵開啟選單

1

2

3

At location

- LateralSource_ID_1 (Lateral Sources)
- Manhole001 (Manholes)
- Pipe_ID_1 (Pipes)

From selection

- LateralSource_ID_1 (Lateral Sources)
- Manhole001 (Manholes)
- Pipe_ID_1 (Pipes)

Chart Region Map Operations Toolbox

設定側入流資料

The screenshot displays the Delft3D FM Suite 2022.04 interface. The main window shows the 'Flow Data' dialog box for a lateral source. The dialog box has the following fields:

- Flow Data
- Type: Q : Constant flow
- Flow [m³/s]: 0.5

The Properties panel on the left shows the following details for the selected lateral source:

- selected Lateral source (1)
- General
 - Name: LateralSource_1D_1
 - Long name
- Administration
 - Branch: Pipe_1D_1
 - Chainage (map): 0
 - Chainage: 0
- Lateral Diffusion
 - Length: 0

The Project tree on the left shows the following structure:

- General
 - 1D
 - network
 - Computational 1D Grid
 - 1D Roughness
 - 1D Initial Conditions
 - 1D Boundary Conditions
 - Lateral Sources
 - 2D
 - Area
 - Grid
 - Bed Level
 - Initial Conditions
 - Boundary Conditions
 - Physical Parameters
 - Sources and Sinks
 - 1D2D Links
 - Output
 - Dimr Run Log
 - FM_model.dia

模式設定檢查 (Validation)

檢視模擬結果 (二維)

檢視模擬結果 (一維渠道)

檢視模擬結果 (一維下水道)

一維模式

Your Turn

Tips:

1. 新增專案
2. 設定投影座標
3. 載入shapefile(定位用)
4. 設置一維渠道及下水道
5. 執行模擬